

INVERSIONS IN ENGLISH THESIS

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Annotation

In English, each member of a sentence, as you know, has a common place, determined by the way it is syntactically expressed, connections with other words and the type of sentence.

Word order is a specific arrangement of words in a sentence, or syntactic group. In English, there is a direct and reverse, or inverted word order. It is associated with the morphological structure of the language and performs a number of important functions in the language, both of a semantic and structural-organizational nature, which emphasizes the relevance of the chosen topic.

Key words

Syntactic relations, stylistic, inversion, speech, text, emotional, expressive, functional.

Some changes in word order change syntactic relations, and with them the whole meaning of the sentence: "When a man wants to kill a tiger he calls it sport; when a tiger wants to kill a man it is ferocity"; others combine grammatical and expressive functions. Compare: "I had known it: Had I known it: If I had known it," where the second differs from the first in grammatical meaning, and from the third in expressiveness. Finally, changes in the order of words are possible, which do not change the grammatical meaning and are not associated with expressiveness or emotionality, but have a functional and stylistic coloring. These include, for example, the assignment of a preposition to the end of a sentence, which is possible only in a colloquial style. Compare: the man of whom I spoke: the man I spoke of.

It is the colloquial style, and especially the familiar colloquial style, that is characterized by the emphasis on the emotionally dominant element in the first place.

☒ "Flowers! You wouldn't believe it, madam, the flowers he used to bring me".

☒ "White! He turned as white as a woman".

A special syntactic form of amplification in such cases is the construction "it is flowers that", "it was flowers that". Such constructions are called emphatic. In the examples considered, the girl first names the object that especially excites

her (flowers), names what struck her most in the reaction of the young man (his pallor), and then explains the situation.

In book speech, on the contrary, a similar effect is created by delay: a psychologically important element is placed at the end of the sentence, which creates some tense expectation, since the reader does not receive the usual indication of the subject of speech at the beginning of the message.

From the point of view of stylistic analysis, only inversion of an expressive, or emotional, or stylistically functional nature is interesting, and not any unusual placement of words. The convention of division into pictorial and expressive means is also found here. As stated above, syntactic means are primarily expressive, but they can also be pictorial. So, numerous cases of inversion in "Alice's Adventures in Wonderland" convey the swiftness of the action in the events described:

☒ She felt that she was dozing off, and had just begun to dream that she was walking hand in hand with Dinah... when suddenly, thump! thump! down she came upon a heap of sticks and dry leaves, and the fall was over.

☒ Alice was not a bit hurt, and she jumped up on her feet in a moment: she looked up, but it was all dark overhead; before her was another long passage and the white rabbit was still in sight hurrying down it. There was not a moment to be lost: away went Alice like the wind (L.Carroll. Alice in Wonderland).

The inversion in the case of "down she came" and "away went Alice" shows the suddenness of the fall and the swiftness of Alice's run and is therefore stylistically relevant. The situation is different with the inversion "before her was another long passage". It is the result of the fact that the sentence begins with the adverb of place. The word order corresponds to the movement from the given to the new, from the topic to the rhyme, that is, it corresponds to the actual division of the sentence and, therefore, turns out to be stylistically neutral.

The term "inversion" should be understood not only as permutations within the predicative core, but also as permutations of secondary members of the sentence, since both functionally and in the English word order system, they have the same syntactic properties.

Both grammatical cases of violation of the usual (fixed) word order (syntactic inversion), and cases of stylistic inversion, also considered in this work, are an interesting object of study for a person who learns a language, as they significantly expand the speaker's capabilities, helping to achieve many goals of his statement. , and the listener (or reader), helping to understand the true meaning of speech (text). The use of this or that word order either draws the

listener's attention to some circumstance of particular importance, or shows the swiftness of action, or creates irony in the sentence, or indicates the emotional state of the speaker and so on.

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